

THE EFFECT OF CATHARSIS IN EXPRESSIVE WRITING AS A STRESS INTERVENTION AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Individuals who are stressed and accompanied by anxiety will become impatient, complain, and think negatively about things around them. Some symptoms of stress are anxiety, restlessness, decreased self-esteem, feeling unable to meet academic demands, irritability, mood swings, frequent panic, and acting without thinking. The purpose of the study was to determine the effect of catharsis in expressive writing as a stress intervention in college students. This type of research is a quasi-experimental research, which is a type of research where the implementation does not use random assignment but uses existing groups. The design of this research is one group pre-test-post-test design. This one group pre-test-post-test design consists of one group that has been determined. The research population in the study was 4th semester students of the Sharia Economics Study Programme at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University as many as 27 students. Data collection techniques in this study by giving pre-test and post-test using an instrument given through Google Form After participating in expressive writing activities, the subject experienced a decrease in the mean score of perceived stress, namely for the pretest of 31.26 and the posttest score of 27.13. Based on the results of hypothesis testing conducted, a significance value of $p=0.026$ ($p<0.05$) was obtained, indicating that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as a stress intervention in college students. The results of hypothesis testing show that there is an effect of catharsis in expressive writing as a stress intervention on college students.

KEYWORDS: Catharsis, stress, students, and expressive writing

INTRODUCTION

The experience of studying at university can be both exciting and nerve-wracking.

University learning requires students to adapt quickly and think independently. They must have consistent motivation to learn and take the initiative to complete the many coursework assignments. If they are not enthusiastic in doing the tasks from lectures, the specified learning outcome targets will not be met. Some students who are unable to keep up with the demands of learning are forced to repeat certain courses because they do not pass the course standards, or even some of them are forced to *drop out of lectures* because they are unable to complete lecture assignments (Mayangsari, 2013).

The opportunity to become a student is a chance for someone to develop their potential while building a career network that can later become a way of life. It is also the momentum of a bridge to future success. However, being a student is not always sweet either, there are tough times to go through. For example, college assignments that come at the same time or the challenge of managing time between doing college assignments or self-development activities outside of college. These complications can be draining, stressful and very challenging (Doygun and Gulec, 2012). Students become vulnerable to psychological disorders, Musabiq and Karimah (2018) found that students often experience fatigue and feel weak due to stress caused by intrapersonal stressors. The experience of the COVID-19 pandemic is a clear example of the number of students experiencing stress, changes in the dynamic learning process were found to make students experience severe stress (referring to the DASS-42 test results) with a high frequency (Sitorus *et al.*, 2023). In addition to intrapersonal factors, Dewi (2016) also found that high stress in students is caused by academic task demands, social environmental pressures and interpersonal pressures. High academic responsibilities, a large task load, social demands, financial problems, and drastic changes in environmental conditions can trigger increased stress in students (Muslim, 2020).

Mills *et al.* (2014) mentioned that stress can cause damage to physiological functions such as stomach pain, arthritis, asthma and headaches. Individuals who are stressed and accompanied by anxiety will become impatient, complain, and think negatively about the things around them. Some symptoms of stress are anxiety, restlessness, decreased self-esteem, feeling unable to meet academic demands, irritability, mood swings, frequent panic, and acting without thinking (Barseli and Ifdil, 2017). Stress has become a difficult part of life to avoid, high levels of stress can be detrimental to the individuals experiencing it (Lin and Huang, 2014). Considering the difficulties faced by university students, there is a need for stress management strategies and relieving negative emotions. This is because hiding or holding back emotions, thoughts, and behaviours is stressful (Pennebaker 2017).

Researchers distributed DASS-21 as an instrument to determine the stress level of students, the distribution of DASS-21 was carried out on 3 May 2023 through *Google form*. After distributing the DASS-21, 27 non-psychology subjects were obtained. The results found that 6 students experienced very severe stress, 5 students experienced severe stress, 4 students experienced moderate stress, no students experienced mild stress and 12 students were in normal stress conditions.

As a stress management strategy, expressive writing has emerged in recent years as an attractive and effective alternative to reduce stress (Bockarov, 2015). Expressive writing means writing some self-expression on a personal book or other contemporary media in a narrated way (Savera *et al.*, 2022). The things written down are positive and negative experiences that result in learning and better health. According to Mukhlis *et al.*, (2020) in

expressive writing, various topics can be written about, but it is very important to explore feelings from objective experiences that write the deepest emotions. Conversations about mental health are currently prominent in various media with a large focus on what we can do to maintain our mental health as well as our physical health. Mental health doesn't always require major life changes or a lot of money. Something, simple writing can relieve stress, reduce anxiety, and help ease feelings of depression (Mohamed *et al.*, 2023). Expressive writing reduces distracting thoughts and can improve memory performance, which in turn can free up our cognitive resources for other mental activities, including our ability to cope effectively with stress (Klein and Boals, 2001).

Pennebaker (1997) found that expressive writing makes individuals tend to use more causal analysis and express more emotions in writing, so psychologists also speculate that expressive writing helps people to simplify and organise fragmented memories. Expressive writing has been shown to help reduce depressive symptoms, when writing down feelings on paper they are easier to analyse and writing down feelings also helps individuals to understand the train of thought that can lead to a worsening mental state (Koschwanez *et al.*, 2013).

The benefit of expressive writing for stress management is that it reduces emotional tension. When you feel overwhelmed thinking about multiple tasks and problems, it can be difficult to think about them. However, putting them down on paper gives you a place to organise your thoughts, rather than letting them stay in your brain all the time. Often people find it difficult to find the words to explain how they feel, or what they are thinking. However, expressive writing exercises help you find the words that allow you to understand your emotions better (Murray, 2002). Therefore, this study aims to determine the effect of expressive writing on stress in university students. The hypothesis of this study is that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as an intervention for stress in university students.

It is hoped that the findings of this study can provide an understanding of the concept of catharsis in expressive writing and can also apply the results of this study in order to bounce back when experiencing stress, so that they can overcome mental health problems experienced independently. In addition, it can be used as a reference by mental health practitioners or educators in the university environment in reducing psychological stress through a simple way in the form of expressive writing.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Stress Theory

Stress theory is a social theory that explains observations about stress, an aspect of social life. Theories use concepts that represent classes of phenomena to explain observations. Stress theory is a relatively new field of theoretical development; it proposed that since the beginning of the human race, people having dealing with stress. Stress theory point to psychological crisis with various forms of humans' emotional problems. According to Boss (2002), Stress theory developed into individual stress theory and family stress theory. Individual stress theory has made valuable contributions to understanding family stress (Boss, 2002). Stress theory here explains the psychological problems facing students in the university as individuals, as they engage in school activities. The study tries to examine the effects of

cathartic in expressive writing as an intervention for stress among university students.

METHODOLOGY

This type of research is *quasi-experimental research*, which is a type of research where the implementation does not use *random assignment* but uses existing groups (White and Sabarwal, 2014). In this study, experimental research methods were used to examine the effect of catharsis in expressive writing as a stress intervention on students of Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University. This research design is a *one group pre-test-post-test design*. This *one group pre-test-post-test* design consists of one group that has been determined. In this design, two tests are carried out, namely before treatment is called a *pre-test* and after treatment is called a *post-test*. the *pre-test* was given to the experimental group (O_1). After the *pre-test*, the researcher gave treatment in the form of expressive writing (X), at the final stage the researcher gave a *post-test* (O_2).

The research population in the study were 4th semester students of the Sharia Economics Study Programme at Sunan Kalijaga State Islamic University as many as 27 students, while the samples involved were students who had qualifications in accordance with the criteria determined by the researcher, namely: non-psychology students, willing to participate in all stages of the experimental process, and have mild to very severe stress levels. After *screening*, a sample of 15 people with mild-severe stress levels was obtained, while the other 12 people did not meet the criteria to become research subjects because they had normal stress levels.

The data collection technique in this study is by giving a *pre-test and post-test* using an instrument given through *Google Form*, namely by using the DASS-21 to measure stress levels in students. DASS-21 has 3 subscales: depression (7 items), anxiety (7 items), and stress (7 items). The stress subscale was developed based on the five dimensions of stress presented by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995), namely: difficulty to calm down, easily agitated / upset, feeling nervous, impatient, and irritable / overly reactive. DASS-21 (*Depression Anxiety Stress Scale-21*) is one of the *self-assessment* instruments by giving a score from 0-3 where: 0: never, 1: sometimes, 2: often or, 3: very often on each item. On the DASS-21 there are 21 items that are asked. The interpretation of stress levels on this instrument is normal, moderate, mild, severe, and very severe.

The procedure in which the researcher adopted was by conducting a screening process using the DASS 21 measuring instrument on 3 May 2023 for 4th semester students of the Sharia Economics Study Program at UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta. After the *screening* process, 15 students passed the research. Before participating in the study, participants were asked for their willingness to participate in the study. The intervention in this study was in the form of expressive writing which was carried out for 5 days on 6 - 11 May 2023. Every day monitoring was carried out by the researcher to ensure that each participant had done expressive writing on that day.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The participants in this study were 4th semester students of the Shari'ah Economics Study Programme at UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta who had mild to severe stress levels.

Table 1. Stress level categorization

Disruption	Severity				
	Normal	Lightweight	Medium	Weight	Very Heavy
Depression	0-9	10-13	14-20	21-27	28+
Anxiety	0-7	8-9	10-14	15-19	20+
Stress	0-14	15-18	19-25	26-33	34+

Table 2. Pre-test and Post-test Results

I	Initials	Pre-test score	Category	Post-test score	Category	Gain Score
	DF	42	Very Heavy	39	Very Heavy	3
	F	42	Very Heavy	35	Very Heavy	7
	KAA	43	Very Heavy	32	Very Heavy	11
	D	19	Medium	17	Lightweight	2
	I	28	Weight	21	Medium	7
	N	27	Weight	24	Medium	3
	YD	23	Medium	19	Medium	4
	ZR	49	Very Heavy	40	Very Heavy	9
	H	27	Weight	27	Weight	0
	QT	29	Weight	30	Weight	1
	M	28	Weight	24	Medium	4
	A	39	Very Heavy	20	Weight	19
	RIS	19	Medium	25	Medium	6
	APM	20	Medium	26	Weight	6

Based on the Table above, 15 students all participated in the study from beginning to end. The results of the *pre-test* and *post-test* showed that 11 students experienced a decrease, 1 student had a fixed pre-test and post-test score, while 3 students experienced an increase in score after being given the *post-test*.

Table 3. Wilcoxon Test

	Pre-test Post-test
Z	-2.232 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-Tailed)	.026

The results of data analysis show that the Z value is -2.232 and the Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) value is 0.026. These results show that $p = 0.026$ ($p < 0.05$), meaning that there is a significant effect of writing catharsis in reducing stress in college students.

This study used a *one-group pretest-posttest* design so that this study only had

one research group. A total of 15 students participated in the study from beginning to end. The results of the *pre-test* and *post-test* showed that 11 students experienced a decrease, 1 student had a fixed *pre-test* and *post-test score*, while 3 students experienced an increase in score after being given the *post-test*. Lovibond and Lovibond (1995) suggest that stress is an individual response to conditions that are considered challenges or threats. Stress arises when individuals experience adjustment or adaptation in any case. When individuals feel pressure in the long term and also the individual's body cannot adapt to it, it will cause stress. Li et al (2016) stress is the condition of the individual when feeling pressure, problems and threats.

Silverman et al (2010) suggest that stress is the body's reaction to changes that require a response, physical adaptation or regulation, psychological, and emotional. Stress can also come from situations, thoughts, conditions or situations that cause frustration, anxiety and nervousness. Hunt and Eisenberg (2010) suggest that the stress experienced by students is related to the problems that have been experienced during lectures. Nur and Mugi (2021) suggest that individuals who have high stress will be dangerous so that it will cause psychological, biological, and social problems.

Participants participated in cathartic writing activities for 5 days. Every day the researcher reminded the subject to write on the expressive sheet that he had for 5 consecutive days and then was given a DASS 21 evaluation *form*. After participating in expressive writing activities, the subject experienced a decrease in the *mean* score of perceived stress, namely for the *pre-test* of 31.26 and the *post-test* score of 27.13. The decrease in the *mean* score is also due to the fact that during expressive writing, the subject is required to be more aware and think positively. Nickerson (2023) suggests that cathartic writing can release negative emotions to relieve intense anxiety, stress, anger, or fear.

In the *pre-test* results, there were 6 students who had very severe stress levels, 5 students had severe stress levels, and 4 students who experienced moderate stress levels. After participating in expressive writing activities for 5 days, there was 1 student who had a mild level and 5 students who had moderate stress. Based on the results of hypothesis testing conducted, a significance value of $p=0.026$ ($p<0.05$) was obtained, which shows that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as a stress intervention in college students. Pennebaker (2017) suggested that expressive writing is a personal and emotional writing skill as an alternative strategy to relieve stress.

CONCLUSION

The results of hypothesis testing show that there is a cathartic effect in expressive writing as a stress intervention for university students. There is a decrease in the *mean* score of stress level from pretest to posttest. Thus, the level of stress experienced by students decreased in the second measurement compared to the first measurement. As a suggestion in future research, it is expected to apply expressive writing activities to be used as a stress coping medium so as not to drag on the stress felt and can rise from adversity.

By applying expressive writing activities, they can live their daily lives with more positive feelings. The shortcomings in the study are that the implementation of cathartic writing is quite short and the collection of cathartic writing is carried out on the last day of the experiment, so the possibility of bias is quite large. In addition, the monitoring of the cathartic

writing process is only through WhatsApp communication, so it cannot be ascertained whether the respondent is doing the writing activity or not.

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